

Scholarly Strategies for Retaining Students in Nepalese Higher Education: A Hermeneutic Phenomenological Study

Man Bahadur Jora*

Abstract: This study explores the practices and measures scholars and students use to stop students from going abroad. This study focuses on ways to prevent students from going to foreign countries to study. At present, students in Nepal seem to go to other countries for further study. It has become a trend that Nepalese universities are increasingly viewed as less preferred institutions. Scholars and graduate students forward diverse measures for stopping students from going on with their studies in the nation. The study employed qualitative research methods, specifically hermeneutic phenomenological research. An interpretive paradigm was employed to analyze the data collected through interview guidelines, under the interview as a tool. There was a lack of skill-based education and employment opportunities. Then, the provision of job fixity and placement and special allowance for unemployed graduates was another theme. The study found that academic institutions used a traditional type of curriculum without focusing on national dimensions. The institutions also did not offer students flexible study hours. In the same way, learning and earning programs were excluded for students in Nepalese universities. Finally, educational institutions need the government's strict educational policy and a semester system-based approach to education in universities.

Keywords: Job opportunities, unemployment, earnings, rewards, noble courses

Introduction

In academic institutions, students study courses that have demands in the market. They deal with social needs and their livelihood. In the same way, they are motivated by their own peers in their life journey. Moment by moment, the requirements of study are changeable with the notions of practicality, usefulness, applicability, effectiveness, and the needs of students and their potential demands. According to Al-Shuaibi (2014), people acquire education in a particular arena to think, feel, and act in styles that scaffold their achievement and enhance their community and personal requirements along with the relevant context. In the words of Hendershot and Sperandio (2009), students study for global citizen identity. Societies need the gems of talent for running in the right direction and waves. University provides education that scaffolds students in their lifelong journey. In the present-day world, the tradition of education is being focused on globalization. But the question is raised: whether universities and academic institutions provide quality education to students or not, and students are led to foreign countries for their education. Social history shapes the attitudes of learners studying abroad (Douglass, 2006). Students have the concept that the education in foreign countries can help them to get their life better and enhanced in the days to come. Regretfully, a large number of recent college graduates claim that they lack the network connections and experiences needed to transition smoothly from college to a working adult (Murphy et al., 2014). Large numbers of Nepali students perceive foreign universities as offering superior academic opportunities, skills, new facilities, and effective teaching methods. In Nepal,

*Corresponding author's email: manjora323@gmail.com

Dr. & Assistant Professor, Far Western University (FWU), Bhimdatta, Kanchanpur, Nepal

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going abroad has become a fashion, and heading abroad for job opportunities is a compulsion. This study aimed at exploring views and realizations of stakeholders on stopping students from going abroad to study, eliciting reasons and measures for students studying in the universities of Nepal, and discovering stakeholders' perspectives on quality education and better job opportunities.

Review of Related Studies

Scholar and Student Perspectives

Different people have different perspectives on the subject matter they face. In the same vein, learners take different things differently. Learners have diverse views regarding their desires and intentions because they hold multiple opinions. The views they perform are perspectives of learners on certain topics. In the present time, students anticipate going abroad for studying and working in English-speaking countries. How students perceive things is essential for further dealings in the educational setting. Perspectives become the ways to deal with the concept, and they show the real takings of people on something. According to Richardson (2003), beliefs are taken as psychological understandings, premises, or propositions that are felt to be true, and they provide learners' autonomy in learning (Jora, 2020). On the other hand, scholars hold the belief that the nation's education policy should prioritize quality.

The beliefs and experiences of scholars in various educational contexts are referred to as the scholar and student perspectives and discourse (Jora, 2022). They involve understanding their thoughts, opinions, and views on topics such as problem-based learning, game-based learning, online learning, and leadership development. These students' common viewpoints serve as a reminder that education is about more than just transmitting knowledge, which is also about appreciating and comprehending the viewpoints of people we are instructing. To establish a welcoming and stimulating learning environment for all students, educators must continually assess their methods and consider their viewpoints. In this connection, Ramirez (2013) argues that through study in foreign countries' experiences, global education has the possibility of preparing students for a globally interconnected world in the international setting to absorb the knowledge.

Stopping Students from Going Abroad

Students have diverse intentions to study courses and go here and there for study in the age of globalization, and the number of students going abroad for study and job opportunities is increasing in Nepal. The universities are not getting more students, and students do not get more interest in studying in Nepal. In the same line, students show more preference to go abroad for job opportunities. Definitely, people search for getting more job opportunities and better and more qualitative education. Normally people prefer less to go to other countries if they get better chances and education that suffice for quality enrichment and engagement. Going abroad is a compelling thing for people of third-world countries like Nepal. Educational institutions need to provide the education, skills, and abilities that students require for further life. They are trusted less by the young generations, and the country does not have the provision of entrepreneurship and employment. Students in Nepal lack faith in the technical aspects of education. It is frightening; frankly speaking, the number of students going abroad is increasing rapidly. Large numbers of Nepali students perceive foreign universities as offering superior academic opportunities, skills, new facilities, and effective teaching methods. This demonstrates that people recognize the opportunity for self-development and cultural immersion that studying abroad offers, and they value the all-encompassing advantages of international education beyond advancing their careers in life (Ikendi, 2022), and language is pivotal for career development (Jora, 2019).

The curriculums and syllabuses are neither studied by students nor analyzed. Even the experts and stakeholders claim that they have designed the qualitative and effective curriculums, courses of study, syllabuses, and languages of learners (Jora, 2020). The reality is that they are modified and drafted late, as I myself realize and find as faculty at a university. The need in Nepal is that the

plan for stopping students from going abroad is a must. A large number of students leave the country to study abroad. The concerned bodies of the country have the necessity of understanding the terrific condition of students rushing for the study. They have plans to amalgamate the courses and include influential subjects. Studying abroad is a sound concept in itself; however, the pervasive mistrust and negligence toward academic institutions are intolerable and are genuinely believed by students and stakeholders. The language of students is very significant for motivating learning (Jora, 2020). The typical programs for providing awareness to students are a great must of the educational mechanism. The educational institutions can establish the international standard meeting programs and streams for students. The universal sides of education are the milestones for the modification of education. The beliefs and responses of the people serve as the foundation for advancing education within the framework of national development.

Job Opportunities as the Baseline of Satisfaction

Along with the education and planning of subject matter, students desire employment and engagement. Academic achievement and quality maintenance are the worthy matters for the job hunters. With the speed of time and the present-day world, the demands and necessities of people are increasing day by day. In Nepal, the young generation is not interested and is directed to the employment sectors of people and guardians. The satisfaction has not been interested in the authentic sides of the authority of the government. Employment possibilities are the chances that people have to obtain work in a certain industry or field, taking into account things like the state of the labor market, the skills needed, and the potential for career advancement. One of the main arguments for international education and study abroad is that it helps students become global citizens (Davies & Pike, 2009; Schattle, 2009).

People do diverse types of jobs, which they undertake for their living or standard maintenance. Students, in particular, go for the life journey that is apt for them. The big question is whether people are satisfied with the job they are engaged in. Most of the people are not enjoying the career they are in. In search of better opportunity, people roam here and there continuously. This is not exceptional in the case of students in the competitive world of today. Students' belief is that they get more and better opportunities in the foreign countries. Nepalese students have a keen interest in going abroad to seize attractive opportunities and secure a prosperous future. They only think about foreign nations and try to achieve the opportunity that is suitable to them. Their ultimate goal is to get them settled in different careers.

Motivation Theory: Maslow's Theory of Hierarchical Needs

Motivation is a regular drive that is required in education and jobs for motivating. Primarily, it is significant to improve productivity, labor, profits, employee retention rates, employee satisfaction levels, and the study desire of students. Along with learning and dealing with job issues, motivation theories are to hunt for what factors drive individuals to study and work towards a goal or an outcome for intended success. They are tracers to seed productive learning and workforce. As a motivational theory, Maslow's hierarchy of needs scheme explains human motivation in the pursuit of diverse layers of needs of individuals. This theory expresses that human beings are driven to fulfill their needs in a hierarchical order. The order commences with the most basic level needs before going on to more sophisticated needs. This theory of Maslow is a content-based motivational theory. In the same token, it outlines a few basic needs an individual wish to fulfill before progressing to more complex needs to which s/he belongs. The hierarchy groups into five levels, which are (Maslow & Lewis, 1987) physiological, safety, socialization, esteem, and self-actualization.

Administrative professionals can grasp their team's goals and strive towards achieving them by applying Maslow's theory of hierarchical needs. In addition to an employee's salary, benefits, and perks, they can plan team-building exercises and professional development. In order to give workers a sense of belonging, managers can start by informing them on a regular basis about plans

or operations. They are able to establish an atmosphere that is inherently favorable to collaboration and teamwork. Work-life balance, growth prospects, and project quality are some of the elements that can inspire a worker to perform well in a position.

Empirical Review of Literature

While developing methodology, research conducted by different scholars becomes a sideways guide to lead the journey ahead. This faculty research cannot be exceptional from this type of ideology. The research trips that I went on thoroughly supported me to sow the seeds for the present study. There are different studies accomplished in the area of studying abroad and getting job opportunities in foreign countries. In this regard, researchers have studied the issue with the different perspectives and beliefs for comprehending practices of stopping students in Nepal.

Lindsey (2005) conducted research entitled “Study Abroad and Values Development in Social Work Students,” aiming at exploring values development in the U.S. and Scottish social work students who studied in a six-year abroad program. Six themes found are allowing oneself to be open to new ideas; being conscious of and insightful about one's own values and opinions; being socially conscious and challenging societal ideals and convictions; respect for diversity, cultural awareness, and anti-discrimination measures; social justice; and the formation of a professional identity. Meibauer et al. (2025) encourage those in international relations (IR) to take a fresh look at what failure and success really mean, as well as their own role in creating an academic environment where scholars from all walks of life can flourish. Drawing from their personal experiences, the contributors highlight the common obstacles that often hinder promising work in the field of IR.

According to Foster et al. (2023), being globally proficient has become crucial in many agricultural science domains. Given the increasing diversity of our education systems' student bodies and the complexity of the global agri-system, we now more than ever require internationally capable educators and learners to build a globally competent workforce and society. Taylor and Revira (2011) sought to find out how students perceive study abroad programs and what barriers might prevent students from applying. The study by Oduwaye et al. (2023) indicates that there has been no progress or change in the difficulties faced by overseas students over the past 21 years, and further study is required in areas like psychological and financial difficulties. Future study directions are proposed, along with a discussion of these issues and other themes identified in the papers.

According to Reuter and Moak (2022), teaching global citizenship has been incorporated into international studies curricula in higher education. According to academics, part of education is developing a global perspective that allows one to critically assess difficult problems in a constantly shifting environment. Although there are disagreements regarding the precise definition of ‘more,’ most people concur that something beyond classroom lectures is necessary to change students' viewpoints. Short-term study abroad programs have developed as a means of providing students with a global experience, particularly those who must juggle the financial constraints of higher education with work, school, and family obligations.

The goal of Mayer's (2025) study is to investigate how students enrolled in Semester at Sea (SAS), a study abroad program, perceive Kenya. Students spend a semester studying on a ship during the four-month study abroad program, travelling to up to 15 countries, including Kenya. Through its academic curriculum, onboard diversity experiences, and land visits to various nations, the SAS program seeks to foster intercultural awareness, cultural learning, and intercultural competencies. The theoretical foundation for this study is developed through the investigation of study abroad participants' perceptions. The results also indicate that the experiences were more reflective of surface-level cultural and national learning than of deep cultural comprehension.

The benefits and difficulties of studying abroad have been examined in the aforementioned studies. They concentrated on the attitudes, effects, benefits, and challenges of studying abroad. They discovered that students who studied abroad produced more good results than unfavorable ones. These studies have demonstrated the various components involved in graduating from international universities. They have demonstrated the achievements, advantages, and difficulties encountered when studying and working overseas. The opinions of Nepalese students regarding preventing students from traveling overseas for postsecondary education and employment possibilities have not been highlighted in any of the research. Evidently, they haven't looked into how well pupils are learning after they graduate from their home nations. Undergraduate students' opinions about deterring students from traveling overseas for further education and employment prospects have not been investigated. I am interested in finding out what Nepalese students think about the title I mentioned when choosing it.

Methodology

This qualitative study employed a hermeneutic phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of undergraduate students. This methodology is beneficial for deducing the realities of student life. Qualitative research, which relies extensively on data, was necessary to investigate this phenomenon (Creswell, 2012). This work incorporated the use of purposive sampling. I derived themes from thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006). This work adopted the interpretive paradigm as its framework. Lather (1986) stated that a research paradigm inherently represents the researcher's beliefs about the current living conditions and their aspirations to achieve them. The interpretive approach presumes that truth and knowledge are subjective, owing to differences in cultural backgrounds and life experiences (Ryan, 2018).

According to Berryman (2019), qualitative questions require responses from interpretive researchers. Understanding the process of 'how' and 'why' is crucial in framing research questions, according to the interpretive method. Interpretations, or interpretive research as we call it, involve researchers expounding on the components of the research. Interpretive research researchers incorporate their personal perspectives into their work because they believe that studying human language can uncover hidden meanings. This is a result of this fact that can be shared and understood in qualitative research (Myers, 2008; Carey, 2012).

This research involved consulting the scholars and students to gather their thoughts on stopping students from going abroad for study. As I was gathering data, I visited my research site and encountered the participants. I initially told them that I wanted to meet them for the purpose of my study. After establishing connections, I attempted to find solutions and ask questions as they appeared straightforward. I introduced myself to them and stated that I wanted to meet them. I made it clear that my intentions would be to keep the introductions confidential. My approach to dealing with students was based on the interview guidelines. The reason I went with this site was for my comfort and knowledge of the students. As a result, I followed the interview guidelines by recording on the audio recorder. In order to complete this study, the scholars and students were consulted and asked for their perspectives on making students stop in the nation. I conducted an interview with them to receive insight into their stance on studying and finding employment outside the country. This study involved 4 participants. Among them, two were graduate students, and two were scholars pursuing PhDs from the university in Nepal. I selected them as I realized the convenience and ease of interviewing them cordially and intensely.

Results and Discussion

I got the information from four participants in Kailali district. Currently, students attend various courses and strive to tackle the issues related to their chosen career path. They incline to hurry to foreign countries for their advanced studies. They are enthusiastic about pursuing education in foreign countries. In the same way, universities and academic students are becoming

less popular study destinations in Nepal. The main focus of this study was on the departure of Nepalese students to other countries for their studies, which was addressed by professors, guardians, and students. I have based the interview process with participants on the guidelines I created for them and on themes identified in data collected in various subheadings.

Theoretical Education and Insufficient Employment Opportunities

Students get education which is useful and effective in real-life situations. Similarly, they require the education that is necessary for a successful life ahead. For that, skill-based education is a basic thing. Universities have courses which just focus on theoretical bases. In Nepal, most of the universities have the same nature, having courses. Though universities conduct courses for getting the needs of people completed, they need to garner the livelihood of them. Skill-based courses are core parts of universities that attract students for studying. That type of asset can handle the internal mechanism of the university or academic institution. Theoretical courses in the present-time scenario cannot rehabilitate the status of the educational institutions. General courses get less attraction of students towards them. The present-time generation runs behind on skills and techniques, which are the basic things of their life.

Students prefer the courses that can offer them opportunities in life. Job opportunities are great matters that can handle the future of students in their academic journey. Students studied and have studied the general subjects and courses in the Nepalese academic institutions. But in the present context, students lure to the courses that can provide the ways for dealing with this advanced world. The ultimate point of students to get engagement in the positions those are suitable for their knowledge. I visited versatile persons and individuals for collecting data required for my study. In line with this, the participant S1 forwarded his words:

At present, fewer students prefer to study the theoretical nature courses. They want to get return from their study. They hope for the courses having practical nature, and they think for the chance they receive after the completion. They have an intention that they can get that chance by studying in foreign countries. Moreover, they have the mindset that foreign universities can have these opportunities. They have the notion that foreign lands mean the collection of pearls.

Students have the desire to flow to new dimensions. Since the verbatim above states, Nepalese universities have courses which are theoretical in nature. This is to focus that students really need modern courses that focus on skill development. On the flip side, the courses themselves are a key part of the reading materials. So, introducing new courses that emphasize practical skills can really resonate with students in today's world. It's clear that students tend to prefer courses that are rich in skills and performance. For them, the subjects they choose to study should align with what's in demand in the job market. Marketable subjects are definitely the ones that pique students' interest.

Lack of Job Placement and Certain Allowance for Unemployed Citizens

Students share their reasons for studying in Nepal, even when opportunities seem scarce. The government plays a crucial role for citizens who are the backbone of the nation. Those struggling to find jobs often feel a lack of status and experience feelings of inferiority. This struggle makes it tough for them to lead a fulfilling life. Overall, unemployed graduates often find themselves frustrated due to the lack of job opportunities.

During my data collection, I spoke with various individuals who participated in this study. They shared their thoughts based on their experiences and insights. I interviewed S2 as part of my research, and S2 mentioned that colleges should work on creating job stability by collaborating with the government. Following my interview guidelines, I asked S2 some questions, and he pointed out that unemployed graduates really need support from the government. In this regard, the participant, S2, explained that:

In Nepal, the main problem is the job placement. There is huge crisis of employment for making hand to mouth. After that, they have jobless conditions and no situations for placing graduates in large number. Students complete the courses, but there is no tradition of job fixity after the graduation. We need the fixed quotas for studying at the universities. If we collect all graduates in one bucket which is not fit for all for providing job

opportunities equally. The government does not have the placement policy. Unemployed graduates need to be provided the certain amount of allowance for their minimum expenditure.

The above verbatim signifies that students prefer job placement after their accomplishment of their qualification. Students studied, have studied and will study if they get job placement. According to the verbatim of the participant S2, students will be ready to stop in Nepal for studying higher education if they have job placement certainty. In Nepal, the big challenge is the job placement when students accomplish their degrees. Similarly, the fixed quotas will produce good human resource and the qualified ones will get the better opportunities. Education producing jobless pile is useless is the concern for today's generation. The main concern is why students study in Nepal if they do not get job opportunities. It can be said that students like to study any courses or streams if they have proper job placement in the suitable areas. On the other hand, the unemployed graduates neither get any allowance nor any job to do. They are ready to work if they are given certain amount of remuneration.

Traditional and Untimely Moderated Curriculum

Our universities have courses, but they are of general nature in the educational arenas. They are unable to modify the courses in time, and the authorities have less interest in implementing new curriculum in the universities. They just run behind power and run for the position in the Nepalese context. Alongside the development of the physical infrastructure of the university, the curriculum can be designed from the inclusion of national issues with international flavor. In every two to four years, the curriculum can have the reformation and monitoring for better application and implementation. The contents are in the curriculum, but they have no policies for practicality.

On the way to collect the data, participants explained that curriculums in the Nepalese universities are outdated and theoretical. Students cannot apply them in their real life problems. In most our curriculums, the contents are from foreign cultures. There is focus on foreigner's culture, styles, and practices. For the more implicational nature courses, national dimensions have to be inserted in our curriculum of the universities. Such dimensions can, to somehow, manipulate students' mind to the Nepalese context and values. In relation to this context, one of my participants, S1, presented the ideas as:

Our universities have no updated curriculums modified timely. They are made without exploring the market value and need. They are designed and there is not continuous implementation. Curriculums are outdated and the moderation and draft committee never come to students and parents for designing. They are theoretical in nature in most of the cases. The contents in our curriculum have included the foreign matters.

The above vignette shows that curriculums in Nepal are traditional in nature, and they do not get moderated timely. The experience of S1 clarifies that courses just include the less moderated contents. In universities, courses and curriculums are changed within one or two-year gap, but that is not the case in the Nepalese context. The contents in the curriculum are just theoretical and irrelevant in the changing world. The participants told that curriculums became unnecessary and uncreative. Moreover, students study the course and pass the exam within the confined examination halls. Ultimately, they have negative attitude towards the country and the education systems. The government is less accountable to the timely moderation of the curriculum.

No Provision of Learning and Earning Programs for Students

In the current scientific and technological environment, Nepali universities only offer education that is unrealistic and pointless. The courses are not part of the system of new, terrible courses for learning and earning degrees. By studying and traveling abroad, students aim to earn more money. Instead of receiving an education there, they intend to receive money in exchange. Nepalese students are in a difficult situation as they scramble to make money. Our universities only concentrate on learning in an impractical manner.

Students look for learning and earning programs at colleges in Nepal. On the one side, students gain knowledge and understanding, and on the other, they have opportunities to make

money. In a foreign country, students can work and pursue their education simultaneously. That is the most ingrained issue in Nepalese kids' minds. They believe that if they can relocate to another country for further education, their lives and incomes will be better. They study and make money together at international universities. The majority of Nepalese students struggle to make money—that is, dollars—by working and studying at international universities. I discovered many students rush to study abroad in order to make money.

In Nepal, students search for educational and financial programs at colleges. While students have the opportunity to earn money, they also acquire information and insight. Students in other countries are able to work and study at the same time. That is the most deeply rooted problem in the brains of Nepalese children. They think their lives and wages will improve if they can move abroad to pursue higher education. Together, they attend overseas universities to study and earn money. Most Nepalese students who work and attend abroad institutions find it difficult to earn money, or dollars. I have found that a good number of students rush to study overseas in order to earn money. The S3 expressed his views as:

Living in the nation is the basic part of life. All people love their country, but they have compulsion. The government has to empower universities with the vision of learning and earning programs. Universities have to start the earning packages for students and have to be ready for memorandum of understanding (MoU) with private institutions and private limited companies. Students of middle class go to foreign countries for earning and getting to have earning. They require the learning and earning programs.

In the present time, students do not like to study without getting anything. The learning without joining without earning are futile for generation of this 21st century. Learning joined with earning is the great interested programs for students to run their studies. Students have the concept that they have good opportunities if they study in the foreign countries' colleges or universities. The expression of S3 also clarified the sense that students liked the studies if they were given chances of learning and earning together in their own ways as they like to work and study together. That facility is not in the context of Nepal and students just are pure students in Nepalese context. Consequently, the students have the final interest to move to the foreign countries for study or move to gulf countries for working.

Lack of Attractive Salary from the job in Nepal

People need job for the management of life. Education policy is the main mechanism of the nation which orients the citizens towards the good destination. Government is the primary part of citizens of any to make the life successful and advanced. Even the government job holders get the salary and allowance that cannot be fit for people in today's life. The satisfaction of the job holders plays important role to make them positive to their services and the nation. They are ready to the works, but have the intentions of getting handsome salaries from the workplace.

In Nepal, the lack of handsome salary is the factor that the job holders do not get the large amount of money. The amount they get is insufficient for hand to mouth for them. The time is changing and goods are becoming expensive. Life style has become advanced in the contour of time frame. Alongside, they have the hope of getting the amount by going the foreign countries. the general tasks cannot facilitate learning and earning income upgrading activities. Regarding this, the S4 expressed:

The policy of the government has to be modified in the case of salaries they get. have to be fellowship and scholarship based. The ministry of finance can manage the good programs to get more salaries for the job holders. The money they get is not sufficient for their livelihood. Students move to the foreign countries to earn the amount they intended. Then, and the programs can be of focusing the life styles of the citizens. Handsome salary is also another important policy that the government has to make for the nation. The good payment is the attraction for attracting good faculties in the institutions.

Government is the patron for citizens of a nation and good policies are the causes of stopping students within the nation. There is need of good payment as salaries in the country. Students are discouraged from the salary system and amount in the nation. Attractive salaries can stop students

in the nation. The policy that can provide students better payment and allowances is the solution of students for engaging in the jobs of Nepalese offices. Systems with attractive payments can stimulate them to struggle in the mother land.

Discussion

In this section, I aim to highlight some research examples to illustrate how my study differs from those that have come before it. For instance, Ecker-Lyster and Nadzeya (2022) explored the perspectives of students from historically under-represented populations, focusing on their experiences while studying abroad. This essay contrasts with my study, which investigates the experiences of stakeholders who are involved in preventing students from going abroad for their education. While both studies look at student perspectives, mine takes a different angle by concentrating on the reasons behind students not going abroad.

Similarly, Lindsey (2005) conducted research titled "Study Abroad and Values Development in Social Work Students", which sought to analyze the development of values among U.S. and Scottish social work students participating in a six-year study abroad program. This also differs from my work, as Lindsey focused on values development, whereas I examined the plans of universities in Nepal to discourage students from studying abroad, along with the reasons for their desire to leave and the measures to keep them in the country. My research specifically sought to identify strategies that would encourage students to stay in Nepal.

Maslow's theory holds significant relevance in this context, as it delineates the hierarchy of human needs, a concept applicable to students' needs and career advancement. The studies I examined revealed that students frequently pursue opportunities abroad, whereas my research seeks to elucidate the strategies and policies of Nepalese universities intended to retain students domestically. Additionally, I explored the underlying causes that drive students to seek education overseas and the strategies that could help them remain in Nepal and tried to present the discussion of findings.

The government of Nepal has focused less on concrete policies to support students staying in the country. The actual rules and guidelines for education in Nepal are still unclear. There's a pressing need for skill-based education within Nepalese institutions. However, universities have yet to clearly define the skills and techniques that students should be learning. Currently, job placement is the top priority for many young people in Nepal, but this focus isn't reflected in the curriculum or in the government's approach to hiring within the national education system. Traditional curricula at Nepalese universities often lack innovation and creativity. They seem to have been developed without considering the actual needs and aspirations of students. Instead of evolving, these courses have remained stagnant for a long time. Students often find themselves studying theoretical subjects that don't translate well into real-life situations. While there are practical elements in the theory, the stakeholders involved are not held accountable for putting them into practice.

The students pursuing both undergraduate and graduate degrees are facing significant challenges. In Nepal, there's limited availability for learning and earnings programs. Many Nepalese students tend to chase after rumors instead of critically analyzing their subjects. They often follow peers who travel abroad for higher education. Unfortunately, local universities and colleges seem to focus more on passing students than on preparing them for the future. The government has not prioritized national policies that would prevent agencies from promoting foreign educational opportunities within the country. Even gold medalists don't receive special recognition or opportunities in their respective faculties. Competitive programs are lacking in the educational landscape. Many students struggle to attend college due to their work commitments. Poverty remains a major hurdle, leading students to believe they must seek jobs in the Gulf and other countries. Institutions have adopted flexible hours, but it's not enough.

The semester system is the standard educational model worldwide, yet students in Nepal miss out on opportunities to study in their preferred universities during these semesters. The integration of information, communication, and technology (ICT) in education is minimal, and the government has not prioritized digitization. The local curriculum is often limited to basic topics, with students primarily focusing on minor issues like political parties and leaders. There's a lack of qualified faculty and effective management in educational institutions. Support for faculty and job holders is virtually non-existent. Nepalese education does not emphasize the idea of learner autonomy. Furthermore, the government has not yet focused on industrial development, and the agricultural sector has not been targeted to ensure a steady supply of human resources.

Conclusion

This study was significant and applicable in the dimensions of research works. This work can garner the wave of staying to study in the country. Good education system is the byproduct of real government rules, plans, and policies. Beyond that, effective policies, creative curricula and employment opportunities are necessary for making Nepalese universities attractive to read and investigate knowledge. This work can encourage to deal with potentialities, challenges and schemes for the development of good schemes for studying in Nepal. Similarly, it provides the experiences of stakeholders on stopping students from studying in Nepal. Particularly, this work can be useful in the enhancement of the education system.

The policies of higher education and curriculums can be formulated and reformulated, and the inclusion of different packages related to this can occur. This study will certainly be a boon for making practice teaching practicable, effective, successful, and goal-based in the days to come, and universities will get inspiration to design novel curriculums and plans in an actual sense. The local governments and educational authorities can use it as a base for making further improvements for studying in Nepalese universities. The Ministry of Education and other institutions which are working for higher education can use it for understanding the situation. This study can contribute to developing schemes, providing funds for students, and establishing industries by launching programs. The future-directed issues can also be studied through the wave of this rigorous work for dealing with gaps related to stopping students from studying in Nepal.

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